

Supplementary information

BODIPY with Tuned Amphiphilicity as Fluorogenic Plasma Membrane Probe

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1. Synthesis:

Synthesis of **1**

A sealed tube in which was added glutaric anhydride (800 mg, 7.017 mmol), dioxane (4 mL) followed by 3-Ethyl-2,4-dimethylpyrrole (14.03 mmol, 2 eq) and $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$ (1.6 mL, 10.52 mmol, 1.5 eq) was allowed to stir at 110°C for 1 hour before being cooled down to room temperature. The sealed tube was open and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (DCM/MeOH: 99/1 to 98/2) and crystallization (DCM/Heptane : 1/1) to obtain 280 mg of **1** (12%) as a red solid. $R_f=0.49$ (DCM/MeOH, 95/5). NMR spectra was in accordance with the literature.¹

Synthesis of the clickable tripod-amine.

A was synthesised according to a described procedure.²

To a solution of **A** (2.44 g, 7.164 mmol) in 10 mL DCM was added TFA (4 mL). The solution was sonicated for 1 minute. The reaction was monitored by TLC (95/5 : DCM/MeOH) and showed the full consumption of the starting material. The solvents were evaporated to provide a beige solid that was used for the next step.

To a solution of **deprotected-A** (1.20 g, 3.438 mmol) in DMF (20 mL) was added β -alanine-Boc (0.649 g, 1 eq) followed by HATU (1.560 g, 4.125 mmol, 1.2 eq) and DIEA (1.8 mL, 10.31 mmol, 3 eq). The reaction was allowed to stir for 1 hour before being evaporated. The product was washed with water and brine and was extracted with EtOAc. The organic phase was dried over MgSO_4 , filtered and evaporated. The crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (Heptane/EtOAc : 5/5) to obtain 1.30 g of **B** (93%) as a white amorphous solid. $R_f=0.39$ (Heptane/EtOAc, 5/5). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 5.76 (s, 1H, NH), 5.25 (s, 1H, NH), 4.14 (d, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 6H, O- CH_2), 3.83 (s, 6H, O- CH_2), 3.36 (q, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H, N- CH_2), 2.46 (t, $J = 2.4$ Hz, 3H, $\text{C}\equiv\text{CH}$), 2.34 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2CO), 1.42 (s, 9H, 3- CH_3). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz; CDCl_3): δ 171.7 (CO), 155.9 (CO-Boc), 79.5 (C alkyne), 79.1 (Cq Boc), 74.8 (CH alkyne), 68.4 ($\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 59.3 (Cq), 58.6 ($\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 37.0 (2 CH_2), 28.4 (CH_3 Boc). HRMS (ES^+), calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{Na}$ [$\text{M}+\text{Na}$] $^+$ 429.2002, found 429.1993.

B (72 mg) was dissolved in 4 mL of DCM and TFA (2 mL) was added. The solution was sonicated for 1 minute and the solvents were evaporated. The crude product was used for the coupling with **1** with no further purification.

Synthesis of 2a, 2b and 2c, general procedure:

To a solution of **1** (30 mg, 0.090 mmol) in DMF (4 mL) was added 2 equivalent of amine (propargylamine or dipropargylamine or the clickable tripod) followed by HATU (1.5 eq) and DIEA (5 eq). The reaction was allowed to stir for 1 hour before being evaporated. The product was washed with water and extracted with EtOAc then dried over MgSO_4 , filtered and evaporated. A fraction of the crude product was directly used for the next step of synthesis. **2a** $R_f=0.51$ (DCM /MeOH, 98/2); **2b** $R_f=0.84$ (DCM /MeOH, 98/2), **2c** $R_f=0.46$ (DCM /MeOH, 96/4)

- The synthesis of **N₃-AZ** was previously described³

Synthesis of amphiphilic BODIPY by CuAAC click chemistry, general procedure:

To a solution of **2** (alkyne BODIPY) in DMF (3 mL) was added **N₃-AZ** (1.2 eq per alkyne) followed by a heterogeneous solution of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 eq) and sodium ascorbate (1 eq) in

water (0.3 mL). The mixture was stirred at 60°C for 1 hour before being evaporated. The crude product was purified by size-exclusion chromatography (DCM-MeOH 1:1) providing pure amphiphilic-BODIPY with no sign of starting material. Due to their amphiphilic nature the product were characterized by ^1H NMR and by high-resolution mass spectroscopy.

B-1AZ: 32 mg, Yield 80%, orange fluffy solid after lyophilization. ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 7.98 (s, 1H, H-triazol), 7.80 (s, 1H, NH), 6.05 (s, 2H, β -H BODIPY), 4.46 (broad s, 4H, 2CH_2 -triazol), 3.49 (broad s, 2H, CH_2), 3.35 (broad s, 2H, CH_2), 3.07 (m, 4H, 2CH_2), 2.92 (s, 3H, $\text{CH}_3\text{-N}^+$), 2.70 (broad s, 2H, CH_2), 2.46 (m, 14H, 4- CH_3 BODIPY, CH_2), 1.95 (broad s, 2H, CH_2), 1.58 (broad s, 2H, CH_2), 1.26 (m, 18H, 9CH_2 C-12), 0.89 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 3H, CH_3 C-12). HRMS (ES^+), calcd for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{64}\text{BF}_2\text{N}_7\text{O}_4\text{SNa}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 798.4699, found 798.4709.

B-2AZ: 39 mg, Yield 68%, orange fluffy solid after lyophilization. ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.09 (broad s, 2H, H-triazol), 7.95 (broad s, 1h, NH), 6.07 (s, 2H, β -H BODIPY), 4.60 (m, 8H, 4CH_2 -triazol), 3.54 (m, 10H), 3.20-3.01 (m, 14H), 2.83 (m, 6H), 2.47 (m, 16H, 4- CH_3 BODIPY, 2CH_2), 2.10 (m, 6H), 1.62 (broad s, 4H), 1.24 (m, 36H, 18CH_2 2-C-12), 0.88 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 6H, 2CH_3 2C-12). HRMS (ES^+), calcd for $\text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{106}\text{BF}_2\text{N}_{11}\text{O}_7\text{S}_2\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 1240.7677, found 1240.7677.

B-3AZ: 46 mg, Yield 82%, orange fluffy solid after lyophilization. ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.20 (broad s, 3H, H-triazol), 7.67 (broad s, 1h, NH), 6.06 (s, 2H, β -H BODIPY), 4.55 (broad s, 12H, 6CH_2 -triazol), 3.80-2.70 (m, 50H), 2.46 (m, 21H), 2.13 (broad s, 6H), 1.92 (broad s, 2H), 1.65 (broad s, 6H), 1.25 (broad s, 54H, 27CH_2 3-C-12), 0.89 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 9H, 3CH_3 3C-12). HRMS (ES^+), calcd for $\text{C}_{90}\text{H}_{161}\text{BF}_2\text{N}_{16}\text{O}_{14}\text{S}_3\text{Na}$ $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 1858.1499, found 1859.1533.

Comparison of the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of the three amphiphilic BODIPYs (400 MHz, CDCl_3) showing the proportional increase of the amphiphilic moiety. The spectra were normalized to the 2 $\beta\text{-CH}$ of the BODIPY. The inset shows the increasing amount of the C-12 chain.

2. Spectroscopy

Figure S1. Non-normalized (left) and normalized (right) Absorption (top) and emission (bottom) spectra of **B-1AZ** in different solvents and environments.

Figure S2. Non-normalized (left) and normalized (right) Absorption (top) and emission (bottom) spectra of **B-2AZ** in different solvents and environments.

Figure S3. Non-normalized (left) and normalized (right) Absorption (top) and emission (bottom) spectra of **B-3AZ** in different solvents and environments.

Figure S4. Dynamic light scattering size measurements of amphiphilic BODIPYs in water (1 μM). Whereas B-1AZ is present as its molecular form, B-2AZ and B-3AZ form soluble nanoparticles in water.

3. Cellular imaging

Figure S5. Laser scanning confocal microscopy images of KB cells stained with the B-1AZ (20 nM) right after addition (A, D). WGA-647 (2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) is a far red emitting labelled lectin used to co-localize the plasma membrane (B, E). A, B and C were taken at middle height of the cell and show the background signal due to the high brightness of B-1AZ in the medium. D, E and F were taken close to the glass surface. The nucleus was stained with Hoechst prior to imaging (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Scale bar is 15 μm .

Figure S6. Laser scanning confocal microscopy images of KB cells stained with the B-3AZ (20 nM) 10 min after addition and taken close to the glass surface showing the presence of aggregates (white arrows). WGA-647 (2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) is a far red emitting labelled lectin used to co-localize the plasma membrane. The nucleus was stained with Hoechst prior to imaging (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Scale bar is 15 μm .

Figure S7. Laser scanning confocal microscopy images of KB cells stained with the amphiphilic BODIPYs (20 nM) 90 min after addition. WGA-647 (2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) is a far red emitting labelled lectin used to co-localize the plasma membrane. The nucleus was stained with Hoechst prior to imaging (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Scale bar is 15 μm .

Figure S8. Laser scanning confocal microscopy of KB cells stained with B-2AZ and B-3AZ (20 nM) and incubated for 3 h and 6 h in OPTI-MEM. The nuclei were stained with Hoechst (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Acquisition and processing parameters were identical. Scale bar is 15 μm .

4. MTT Cytotoxicity assay

Figure S9. KB cells viability in the presence of B-2AZ, Triton 1% was used as a positive control of cytotoxicity. Cell viability is expressed in percentage of cell viability in reference of the control (no dye, DMEM+ 0,5% DMSO).

Figure S10. Photostability of B-2AZ. KB cells were stained with B-2AZ (20 nM) and were imaged with laser scanning confocal microscope for 15 minutes upon continuous illumination (340 frames, 2 scans per frame, laser power was 5% (488 nm). Scale bar is 15 μm . The frame number is indicated on the top left of images. The graph (bottom right) is the normalized mean fluorescence intensity upon imaging, which shows a decrease of less than 10%. See also supplementary movie 2.

Figure S11. Two-photon excitation imaging of fixed HeLa cells (PFA 4%) fluorescently labeled with B-2AZ (100 nM). Two-photon excitation was at 1000 nm and emission was collected from 495 to 560 nm.

5. NMR and mass spectra

¹H NMR spectrum of **B-1AZ**

HRMS spectrum of **B-1AZ**

¹H NMR spectrum of **B-2AZ**

HRMS spectrum of **B-2AZ**

^1H NMR spectrum of **B-3AZ**

HRMS spectrum of **B-3AZ**

6. References

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